

**Empowering
Europe's Data
Future**

D5.1 LEGAL ASSESSMENT AND RECOMMENDATIONS ON BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGIES

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D5.1 LEGAL ASSESSMENT AND RECOMMENDATIONS ON BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGIES

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, led by KU Leuven, is a public report scheduled for Month 18 of the project. Its primary objective is to present the findings and recommendations from Task 5.1, which focuses on the legal assessment of blockchain technologies.

Task 5.1, also spearheaded by KU Leuven with contributions from partners AIR, USAL, POLITO, NET-INTRA, ARCTUR, and INESC TEC, runs from Month 1 to Month 16 of the project. The core objective of this task, and consequently of this deliverable, is to conduct a thorough legal assessment of the technical possibilities that arise from combining blockchain technology with cloud services, in alignment with the European Commission's overarching blockchain strategy.

This assessment involves a detailed examination of various critical legal frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the NIS2 Directive on cybersecurity, and the Data Act (DA) proposal, with a particular focus on their impact on smart contracts. The deliverable will explore potential frictions and challenges that may arise between existing legal frameworks and Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), with a specific focus on GDPR compliance. Furthermore, it will integrate insights from relevant EU initiatives, such as the EU Blockchain Observatory and Forum, as well as the Guidelines of the European Data Protection Board on Personal data processed through Blockchain technologies.

Ultimately, Deliverable 5.1 aims to provide a clear, comprehensive, and actionable legal and regulatory framework for the responsible deployment of blockchain technology within the evolving landscape of Data Spaces.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AG	Advocate General
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AML	Anti-Money Laundering
AMLD	Anti-Money Laundering Directive
CFT	Countering the Financing of Terrorism
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CNIL	Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés (The French Data Protection Authority)
DA	Data Act
DGA	Data Governance Act
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
ETH	Ethereum
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IAB	Interactive Advertising Bureau (The document refers to "IAB Europe")
ID	Identity / Identification
IP	Internet Protocol
ISO	International Standards Organisation
ISO	International Standards Organisation
KYC	Know Your Customer
NFT	Non-Fungible Tokens
PET	Privacy-Enhancing Technology
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
POA	Proof of Authority
POS	Proof of Stake
POW	Proof of Work

SRB	Single Resolution Board
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
TCF	Transparency & Consent Framework
US	United States
WP29	Article 29 Working Party
ZKP	Zero-Knowledge Proof

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, blockchain technology has emerged as a promising avenue for enhancing data security, privacy, and transparency. As blockchain provides a decentralised and immutable ledger system, it offers unique benefits, such as data integrity, especially when combined with other applications, like cloud solutions, e.g., computing and storage, facilitating the sharing and exchange of data across various entities. For instance, in a healthcare ecosystem, patient records are stored in a cloud database. By integrating blockchain, hospitals, healthcare workers, and potentially insurance providers can access a shared ledger, i.e. blockchain, that ensures the data is tamper-proof and consistently updated. Therefore, the combination is believed to ensure that all parties view the same, unaltered record, thereby increasing trust, reducing duplication, and enabling faster decision-making.

However, its proliferation presents complex legal challenges that must be carefully navigated. This legal analysis examines the regulatory landscape governing blockchain technology, exploring the potential legal implications and addressing the most critical issues of data protection, privacy, and compliance with existing laws. By scrutinising the intersection of these technologies, this analysis aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the legal considerations essential for leveraging blockchain in combination with cloud effectively and lawfully, instilling a sense of caution and responsibility in dealing with these technologies.

This legal analysis begins with an in-depth examination of blockchain's function within the NOUS framework, emphasising its pivotal role in data value tracking, immutability, and integrity. These attributes bring substantial added value but also necessitate a thorough understanding of the legal landscape. A review of relevant data protection laws, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other selected data laws such as the Data Governance Act (DGA) and the Data Act (DA), provides a foundational understanding of the regulatory environment. Additionally, the analysis will consider the current state of the art in the literature regarding data protection issues associated with blockchain technology.

While the use of blockchain in combination with cloud technologies can amplify the benefits, it can also exacerbate potential risks. This analysis aims to assess the risks to fundamental rights and freedoms, such as data security and privacy, and to identify any areas of legal ambiguity.

Our methodology involves a specific use case (in Part II), which entails processing sensitive emergency response data in a crisis management setting with significant societal implications. This use case has been created to provide meaningful insights into the potential impacts and challenges of integrating blockchain into cloud applications, as well as the corresponding use case #3 of NOUS.

The roadmap for this analysis encompasses an overview of relevant technologies, a comprehensive review of EU legislation, identification of key legal issues, a detailed legal evaluation of risks, and a synthesis with concluding remarks. The ultimate aim of the study is to provide a clear understanding of the legal considerations and implications of leveraging blockchain technology in the context of cloud computing and data spaces.

PART I: THE EU LEGAL FRAMEWORK APPLICABLE TO BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY AND CLOUD PLATFORMS

1. BLOCKCHAIN: A TECHNICAL OVERVIEW

This section provides a technical overview of blockchain technology, examining its core functions, including data value tracking, immutability, and integrity. It explores how these features enhance the operational capabilities of cloud computing and *vice versa*. This technical foundation will set the stage for the subsequent legal analysis and assessment of associated risks and compliance issues.

1.1 DEFINITIONS AND KEY CONCEPTS

According to the International Standards Organisation (ISO), a blockchain is a distributed ledger in which confirmed blocks are organised in an append-only, sequential chain using cryptographic links. [1] In simpler terms, a blockchain functions as a digital, shared database distributed across the Internet and maintained by numerous network participants, known as nodes, within a peer-to-peer network. This decentralised structure ensures that the data stored on the blockchain is both secure and transparent.

Blockchain relies on established cryptographic techniques to enable the participants in a network to connect and interact with one another without a pre-existing trust or relationship. These techniques include public-key infrastructures, hash functions, digital signatures, consensus algorithms and zero-knowledge proofs. To begin the process, one of the involved participants generates a block. Then, additional nodes validate the block. Finally, the validated block is added to a chain maintained throughout the internet, creating a unique record with a unique history. [2], [3]

1.2 TYPOLOGY OF BLOCKCHAIN SOLUTIONS

Blockchain solutions are subject to a wide array of technologies and techniques, which affect the governance capabilities of each participant or actor in the network. To begin with, the main difference between distributed and decentralised systems is crucial to understanding the technological underpinnings and governance of blockchains. According to Gochhayat and others, the degree of decentralisation can be measured across governance, network and storage layers using various metrics.[4] For instance, the internet is better understood as distributed, both technologically and in governance.[5] Distributed systems often aim to combine the advantages of centralised and decentralised approaches. In blockchains, users or nodes can collectively agree on the content.

Distributed ledger technology (DLT) is often used interchangeably with blockchains. DLTs are databases that store data sequentially. Distributed ledgers refer to a collective way of storing and managing data. They can be designed as linear or network types, e.g., Directed Acyclic Graphs.[2] Blockchains are formed in a linear design, but are databases supported by a distributed

network of computers.¹ They are the most common ledger designs in the market.² Simply put, blockchain is a digital shared ledger that is distributed and kept across many network members, known as nodes, in a peer-to-peer network.[6]

The chain can be open to anyone (permissionless), as in the cases of Bitcoin or Ethereum, or it can only be open to specific stakeholders, i.e., permissioned or private.[7] It can also be public, private, or consortium (hybrid). For example, in public blockchain networks, any individual might theoretically download the specified open-source software and engage in the network, receiving a private and public key and gaining access to the stored data.[1] A private blockchain, on the other hand, is only accessible to a limited group of users.[1] Again, these categories can be both permissioned or permissionless.[1] For example, a public blockchain can be permissioned, in which authorisation is required to join the network. Permissioned blockchains might serve as the foundation for services that use timestamped registries. As will be analysed in Part II, developers will settle on a trade-off among different features based on the service they intend to provide.

1.3 WALLETS AND THE PUBLIC KEY INFRASTRUCTURE (PKI)

Wallets are tools, either software or hardware, that enable users to generate, manage, store, and use their cryptographic keys—both private and public—and control the assets contained within them.[8] These wallets interface between the user and the blockchain, facilitating secure transactions and asset management.

For example, users must first download or own a wallet to conduct a Bitcoin transaction. Upon creating a wallet, both a public key and a private key are generated within it. The public key functions as a unique address, similar to an email address, that is publicly known and can be shared with others to receive funds. In blockchain networks, nodes employ Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) to begin and recommend transactions.[9] Every participant is assigned a unique pair of keys: a public key, which serves as their address and is accessible to other nodes, and a private key, which is used to verify their identity.[10]

1.4 CONSENSUS AND TRANSACTION

When a transaction begins, it must contain the initiator's public key, the recipient's public key, and the transaction's content. These elements are collectively encrypted using the initiator's private key and then distributed to the other nodes. The other nodes will confirm the transaction using proven cryptographic algorithms, i.e., consensus protocols.[11] The nodes must follow a procedure for obtaining a consensus on the final state of the ledger.[12] Once the nodes approve the transaction, it is executed. Following execution, a new block is immediately added to the network, compressing the transaction. This procedure is performed each time for every approved transaction, contributing to the ongoing growth and integrity of the blockchain ledger.[6]

² Blockchain is used sometimes with a capital B, referring to the original Bitcoin Blockchain. (the Blockchain).

1.5 ON-CHAIN OFF-CHAIN GOVERNANCE AND DATA

Blockchains typically deploy combinations of different technologies for storage and governance options. Off-chain and on-chain data refer to where the data related to a blockchain are stored and accessed. As the name implies, on-chain data refers to the information stored (and often validated) on a blockchain. For example, transaction data that contains details of cryptocurrencies (e.g., sender, receiver, amount); smart contracts' code and state data, and block data, e.g., metadata, block number, timestamp and hash of the previous block are typically stored on-chain. On the contrary, off-chain data refers to data that is stored outside of the blockchain, but that is still linked to the blockchain. Off-chain data can be stored in local databases or the cloud. [13]

In the context of blockchains, governance models play a critical role in shaping how decisions are made regarding the development and evolution of the network. Two primary governance models are often discussed: on-chain governance and off-chain governance. Both models offer distinct approaches to decision-making, each with its own strengths and limitations.

On-chain governance refers to the process of decision-making that takes place directly on the blockchain. In this model, stakeholders (e.g., token holders, miners) vote on proposals, protocol upgrades, or other governance matters through transactions recorded on the blockchain. Off-chain governance refers to the decision-making process that occurs outside of the blockchain.

This can include discussions, informal agreements, and voting mechanisms that are not recorded on the blockchain itself. For instance, in many cryptocurrencies, discussions take place between various stakeholders, such as developers and the broader community, before reaching a consensus. These discussions are considered off-chain as they occur in online forums outside the blockchain. [6]

2 REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

2.1 OVERVIEW

In this section, our main purpose is to explain that the EU legal framework might apply to the blockchain use case of the project. Thus, this section scrutinises the elements in the material scope of the GDPR and LED. It also sets the scene for the legal analysis in Part II by demonstrating that blockchain technology might process personal data. Following this subsection, we address the most prominent legal issues identified in the literature regarding the compatibility of blockchain-based personal data processing with the GDPR. This section, however, only provides general descriptive text, not yet applying the legal framework to the specific use case in NOUS (use case #3). As the data protection framework and the technology in question, i.e., blockchain, are highly complex, a detailed legal analysis is conducted in Part II, taking into account the specifics of the use case.

The second part of the regulatory framework outlines other relevant EU legislation relevant to data sharing, regardless of being decentralised or centralised, in the public and private sectors.

2.2 Material scope of the EU data protection framework

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies to all processing of personal data in both the public and private sectors within the Member States of the European Union. However, there are specific exceptions to its applicability.

Exceptions to the GDPR include:

- **Activities Outside the Scope of EU Law:** This includes data processing activities carried out in the exercise of activities not governed by EU law, such as national security, defence, and other activities classified as outside the scope of the EU.
- **Household Activities:** The GDPR does not apply to data processed by a natural person in the course of purely personal or household activities.
- **Law Enforcement Directive (LED):** The LED refers to processing activities carried out for the purposes of law enforcement, which are instead governed by the Law Enforcement Directive (Directive (EU) 2016/680). GDPR and LED are both components of the European Data Protection Framework; they have distinct but complementary scopes.

The LED specifically deals with personal data processing by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection, or prosecution of criminal offences and the execution of criminal penalties. The LED's purposes may thus include preventive police activities aimed at protecting against threats to public security that could result in a criminal charge (such as police activities at demonstrations, sporting events, and maintaining public order) as well as processing operations performed for these purposes.

As will be seen in Part II of this document, some transfers of personal data, initially collected under the GDPR, and subsequently transferred to law enforcement authorities would still fall under the material scope of the GDPR, since the exclusion in Article 2(2)(d) GDPR only refers to the processing of personal data "by competent authorities".^[14]

2.3 PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA BY BLOCKCHAIN

The GDPR applies to the *processing of personal data*, wholly or partly by automated means and other than by automated means when the personal data form part of a filing system or are intended to form part of such a system (Article 2(1) GDPR). The concepts of personal data and processing are important for any assessment of the material scope of the GDPR.

Personal data, as defined under Article 4(1) GDPR is any information relating to an "identifiable natural person (data subject)". To determine if data relates to an identifiable individual, one must consider "all the means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, either by the controller or by another person to identify the natural person directly or indirectly." This determination should account for objective factors like costs, time required for identification, current technology, and future technological developments (Recital 26 GDPR).³

³ See for relevant case law: Case C-582/14 ECLI:EU: C:2016:779 Judgment of the Court (Second Chamber) of 19 October 2016 Patrick Breyer v Bundesrepublik Deutschland.

The CJEU interprets the concept very broadly. Personal data may consist of several pieces of data that, separately, do not identify an individual. The Court found in the *Breyer Case* that “*there is no requirement that all the information enabling the identification of the data subject must be in the hands of one person.*”⁴ Therefore, if multiple pieces of distinct information pertain to a specific individual, these pieces must collectively identify that person when combined. To provide some examples, the image of a person recorded by a camera,⁵ information related to income⁶ and tax⁷ of persons, records of working hours,⁸ IP addresses,⁹ fingerprints¹⁰ were qualified as personal data under the case law.

Other concepts related to the scope of the GPPR are the concepts of **pseudonymous and anonymous** data, which are often perceived as confusing. Pseudonymisation is the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable person. Article 32 defines pseudonymisation as a security measure to be taken by the data controller. In this technique, specific personal data can be replaced by a certain indicator such as numbers, or nicknames. When data are pseudonymised, they still qualify as personal data since the natural person could be indirectly identified.

The GDPR does not apply to data that are anonymised, which means the modification of personal data that can be achieved by several techniques e.g., randomisation or generalisation. However, the lines between pseudonymisation and anonymisation remain blurry to date and it is useful to keep in mind that once anonymised data can qualify as pseudonymised data, thus personal data, depending on the state of the art. Hence, these concepts are not carved in stone and their existence can be considered fluid rather than certain.[15]

Considering the definitions provided in the GDPR, and of the interpretation of the CJEU, most data processed by blockchains are also considered personal data about the GDPR. Previous studies posited that hashed, public, and private key data are pseudonymous, and thus they are covered by the GDPR. Below, we explain these categories of data and the discussion in more detail.

Finck discerns two types of data that may qualify as personal and thus governed by GDPR: transactional data or additional data, and public keys are stored in a blockchain. As explained, blockchain generally uses addresses generated from public keys for identifying a natural person. Whereas the GDPR does not apply to anonymised data, cryptographic hash functions, which are essential for blockchain technologies, achieve merely pseudonymisation.

Basically, these data are encrypted and considered personal data under the GDPR since the data subject can still be identified. To illustrate further, even if personal information consists just of reference ID numbers, such identifiers are usually unique to a single person. Consequently, both public keys and transactional data stored on blockchains are subject to the GDPR, as widely accepted by scholars and institutions.

⁴ Judgment of 19 October 2016 *Breyer*, C-582/14, EU:C:2016:779, para.43.

⁵ Judgment of the Court (Fourth Chamber), 11 December 2014, *František Ryneš v Úřad pro ochranu osobních údajů*, C-212/13, EU:C:2014:2428, para. 22.

⁶ Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 16 December 2008, *Tietosuojavaltuutettu v Satakunnan Markkinapörssi Oy and Satamedia Oy*, C-73/07, EU:C:2008:727, para. 35.

⁷ Judgment of the Court (Third Chamber), 30 May 2013, *Worten*, C-342/12, EU:C:2013:355 para.19.

⁸ Judgment of the Court (Third Chamber) of 24 November 2011, *Scarlet*, C-70/10, EU:C:2011:771, para. 51.

⁹ Judgment of the Court (Fourth Chamber), 17 October 2013, *Michael Schwarz v Stadt Bochum*, C-291/12, EU:C:2013:670, para.27.

¹⁰ Judgment of the Court (Third Chamber) of 1 October 2015, *Smaranda Bara and Others v Casa Națională de Asigurări de Sănătate and Others*, C-201/14, EU:C:2015:638, para. 29.

The term processing is also defined by the GDPR Article 4(2), rather broadly as "any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or sets of personal data," including collection, recording, deletion, and storing. In the context of blockchain, the first addition of personal data to a wallet or ledger, the storage of hashes and public keys, the transfers through nodes and the update across the network should therefore be deemed personal data processing.

2.4 OVERVIEW OF THE LEGAL ISSUES: BLOCKCHAIN VS. GDPR

Blockchain and GDPR share the goal of enhancing user control over personal data.[16] According to a systematic literature review study conducted based on 114 papers by Belen Saglam and others, some issues can be identified in the tension between GDPR and blockchain.[3]

First of all, blockchain technology poses challenges to compliance with the GDPR due to is the difficulty in identifying data controllers and processors. Opinions vary, with some researchers suggesting that all nodes could be considered joint controllers, while others argue that developers or specific types of nodes (e.g., miners) should bear this responsibility.[3]

The second issue is immutable data storage; ensuring data subject rights like the right to erasure (Article 17) becomes practically impossible. Thus, the challenge has to do with reconciling blockchain's immutability with GDPR requirements.[16], [17], [18]

While some argue that processing personal data on blockchains inherently violates the GDPR,[17] others suggest that blockchain is not necessarily incompatible with GDPR, emphasising the need for case-by-case analysis and potential reinterpretation of data protection concepts in the context of distributed systems.[6]

(I) WHO IS THE DATA CONTROLLER IN BLOCKCHAIN?

The GDPR is predicated on the idea that in each data processing activity, there is always at least one natural or legal person ("data controller") accountable for GDPR compliance, which can be requested to implement the rights of data subjects. [9] The GDPR defines this entity as any natural or legal person that determines the purposes and means of processing personal data. Where the purposes and means of processing are determined or influenced by more than one controller, the controllers are deemed to be jointly responsible under Article 26 of the GDPR.

A. CASE LAW ON CONTROLLERSHIP

Insights from the case law of the CJEU can be consulted here to gain a deeper understanding of the allocation of responsibility under the GDPR. As mentioned, more than one entity can determine the purposes and means of the processing. Where the purposes and means of the processing are determined (or influenced) by more than one entity,[19] joint controllership occurs. Jointly is interpreted as 'together with' or 'not alone.' [3] As this notion has been introduced to address the multiplicity of actors in contemporary processing networks, its interpretation is crucial for understanding the roles in blockchains.

The concept of joint controllership has evolved through guidelines and case law, and it can manifest itself in different ways. The overarching criterion for joint controllership is factual influence over the processing. While joint controllers must define their respective duties through arrangements, these formal agreements should always be compared against the actual circumstances. WP29 states that processing operations must be examined both at the micro- and macro-level. Even though certain processing operations may appear disconnected at the micro-level as they have different purposes, one should "double-check whether at the macro-level these processing operations should not be considered *a set of operations* pursuing a joint purpose or using jointly defined means."

The "phase-based approach" to controllership, developed by the CJEU, is a method for assessing data processing operations by breaking them into distinct stages or steps. This method aims to prevent entities from being held responsible for processing operations where they have little information or influence. [20]

To illustrate, it might be useful to dissect the stages of processing. According to Article 2, GDPR processing means *'any operation or set of operations which is performed upon personal data, whether or not by automatic means, such as collection, recording, organisation, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, **disclosure by transmission**, dissemination or otherwise **making available**, alignment or combination, blocking, erasure or destruction.'*

Control over each of these stages may have a partial influence on the processing while having a different purpose and/or means. In the *Fashion ID case*, a commercial website operator who embedded a Facebook *like-button* (social plugin) on its website was qualified as a joint controller. The CJEU acknowledged in this case that *[the joint controllers] may be involved at different stages of that processing of personal data and to different degrees, with the result that the **level of liability of each of them must be assessed with regard to all the relevant circumstances of the particular case.***¹¹

The Court also confirmed that being a joint controller does not equate to sharing equal responsibility. The CJEU determined that Fashion ID could not establish the purposes or key aspects of the data processing performed by Facebook Ireland after the data transfer. As a result, the Court concluded that Fashion ID could not be regarded as the controller for this specific processing activity, since it was conducted solely by Facebook.¹²

However, Fashion ID was still identified as a joint controller with Facebook Ireland concerning the processing operations related to the collection and transmission of personal data to Facebook Ireland. It was ruled that Fashion ID and Facebook Ireland jointly determined the purposes and essential elements of those processing activities operations.¹³

Moreover, regarding the related controller obligations, the CJEU stated that Fashion ID, acting as a joint controller for the processing operations it participates in, must provide specific information to page visitors at the time of data collection. This includes details such as the operator's identity and the purpose of the processing operation.¹⁴

In the *IAB Europe case*, IAB Europe established the Transparency & Consent Framework (TCF), which is a set of rules for processing personal data related to user consent. TCF includes technical specifications for collecting and processing user preferences and also sets rules for storing and sharing the Transparency and Consent String (TC String).¹⁵ IAB Europe consists of members, such as website and application providers, data brokers, and advertising platforms, who have access to personal data.

Because IAB Europe influences the processing of personal data through the TCF and determines, along with its members, the purposes and means of processing, it is classified as a joint controller. As they participate in the processing, such as generating and using TC Strings, the members are also considered joint controllers. These members also use the platform for purposes like targeted online advertising.¹⁶

¹¹ Fashion ID para 70; judgment of 10 July 2018, *Jehovan todistajat*, C-25/17, EU:C:2018:551, para 66.

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Ibid.* para 101.

¹⁵ JUDGMENT OF THE COURT (Fourth Chamber) 7 March 2024 (*) Case C-604/22, *IAB Europe*, ECLI:EU:C:2024:214, para 21.

¹⁶ JUDGMENT OF THE COURT (Fourth Chamber) 7 March 2024 (*) Case C 604/22, *IAB Europe*, ECLI:EU:C:2024:214, para 31.

The court makes a distinction between the initial processing of the TC string and the subsequent processing by third parties. The processing of personal data may consist of one or more operations, each relating to a different stage. IAB Europe is involved in the initial stage of processing of personal data when the consent preferences of the users are recorded in a TC String, but not necessarily in the subsequent processing by third parties.¹⁷

However, a joint controller must have its own processing purpose, which is essential for differentiating it from a processor. A processor acts solely on behalf of the controller and does not establish the processing purpose. For instance, Fashion ID gained more visibility, whereas Facebook used the gathered data for its own business objectives.

Yet, mutual benefit does not equate to mutual purpose. The EDPB clarifies that simply having mutual benefits (e.g., commercial) from a processing activity does not inherently result in joint responsibility controllership.^[21] Nevertheless, processing for commercial interest implies purpose. For example, in the *Wirtschaftsakademie Schleswig-Holstein*, a German company specialising in education, used a Facebook fan page to provide its services. Administrators of the page accessed anonymous statistical data about visitors through Facebook Insights, a free tool offered by Facebook under non-negotiable terms. This tool utilised cookies containing unique user codes stored on visitors' devices for up to two years to collect data.¹⁸

In the *Wirtschaftsakademie Schleswig-Holstein* case, the Court took the view that the fan page administrator on Facebook was a joint controller, as this action contributed to processing personal data along with Facebook.¹⁹ However, the fan page administrator could not access personal data. The Court held again that joint responsibility does not imply equal responsibility. Only making it possible to process personal data or enabling the control of the main controller was seen as sufficient to qualify as a joint controller.²⁰

The Court relied on the same reasoning in *Jehovan Todistajat*, stating: "*Natural or legal person who exerts influence over the processing of personal data, for his own purposes, and who participates, as a result, in the determination of the purposes and means of that processing, may be regarded as a controller [...]*."²¹

A crucial factor for establishing joint control is that the processing cannot occur without the involvement of both parties; their purposes must be inextricably linked. This implies that joint controllers must share a mutually closely aligned or complementary objective. Essentially, this pertains to how the objectives of various controllers are interrelated and connect to the overall processing operation. In my opinion, this can be understood as a form of dependency, where the actualisation of one controller's purpose relies on another controller's processing and vice versa. An example of this type can be seen in the enabling function discussed in the Fashion ID or SWIFT cases, where one joint controller does not exercise direct control over personal data but plays a role in the chain of processing. In Fashion ID, for example, the CJEU clarified that a website operator participates in determining the purposes because, without their joint operation, Facebook could not process the data in question.^[22]²²

¹⁷ JUDGMENT OF THE COURT (Fourth Chamber) 7 March 2024 (*) Case C 604/22, IAB Europe, ECLI:EU:C:2024:214, para 21.

¹⁸ Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 5 June 2018 C-210/16, Unabhängiges Landeszentrum für Datenschutz Schleswig-Holstein v Wirtschaftsakademie Schleswig-Holstein GmbH, ECLI:EU: C:2018:388, para.15.

¹⁹ Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 5 June 2018 C-210/16, Unabhängiges Landeszentrum für Datenschutz Schleswig-Holstein v Wirtschaftsakademie Schleswig-Holstein GmbH, ECLI:EU: C:2018:388, para 43.

²⁰ Ibid. para 43.

²¹ Case C-25/17 *Jehovan Todistajat* [2018] ECLI:EU:C:2018:551

²² Similarly, in the *Jehovan Todistajat*, the CJEU considered whether a religious community was a controller in arranging preaching activities. The community claimed that the preachers collected the personal data individually without any disclosure to the community, meaning the processing was "entirely beyond [their] control".²² Case C-25/17 *Jehovan Todistajat* [2018] ECLI:EU:C:2018:551, para 60-73.

Finally, these decisions should have a substantial impact on determining the purposes and means of the processing. This can be interpreted as having a practical effect on the processing. Facilitating access to or sharing data (along with the associated purpose) is considered substantial enough to establish controllership. In contrast, mere access to the data might not suggest any such implication controllership.²³ For example, processors may have access to the data, but such processing is conducted on behalf of the controller, meaning that the processor has no autonomous purpose. Another example involves the recipients to whom the data are disclosed and who are subject to the instructions of the controller, such as an employee. However, the recipients may also include third parties who are authorised to access personal data held by the controller. Therefore, mere access does not imply control unless there is no separate purpose for the processing.

The possibility that one of the entities may, in practice, have no access to personal data could be of particular importance when determining its level of responsibility within the processing operation, but not in establishing its joint controllership role.[23]

For instance, in the *Wirtschaftsakademie Schleswig-Holstein* case, the Court held that the fan page administrator on Facebook was a joint controller, as this action contributed to the processing of personal data alongside Facebook.²⁴ However, the fan page administrator was unable to access the personal data. The Court held that joint responsibility does not imply equal responsibility. Only making it possible to process personal data or enabling the main controller to control it was seen as sufficient.

2.4.1.1 SCHOLARLY DEBATE

It has been discussed in the literature whether it is possible to hold the blockchain nodes responsible.[9], [16] In principle, nodes that can determine the purposes and means of processing personal data should be considered data controllers under the GDPR. However, determining which nodes can be considered controllers under the GDPR might be perplexing, as it depends on various parameters.

Scholars state that in the case of private blockchains, it may still be possible to identify a central intermediary who can be considered a data controller, such as the operator of a system who receives the claims of data subjects.[9] In public blockchains, regardless of whether they being permissioned or permissionless, there is no one point of control. However, in public and permissionless blockchains, it may be more challenging to determine which node is the controller, as anyone can participate in the network and validate transactions. As will be discussed in Part II, this is different in permissioned blockchains, as network access is restricted to a particular group of participants.

Nodes are either active participants in blockchain governance, e.g., full nodes, or passive agents subject to the commands of software created by developers.[9] For instance, some nodes, such as the miners in the Bitcoin network, validate transactions based on mathematical puzzles to maintain the ledger. Others simply store a copy of the blockchain. On the other hand, these nodes determine whether to join the network and choose which function or goal to pursue within the network. For

²³ Judgment of the Court (Second Chamber) of 29 July 2019. Case C-40/17 Fashion ID GmbH & Co.KG v Verbraucherzentrale NRW eV, ECLI:EU:C:2019:629, para 69.

²⁴ Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 5 June 2018 C-210/16, Unabhängiges Landeszentrum für Datenschutz Schleswig-Holstein v Wirtschaftsakademie Schleswig-Holstein GmbH, ECLI:EU: C:2018:388, para.15.

example, some of these nodes may choose to play a role in executing smart contracts containing personal data.

Finck states that nodes do not establish applicable rules in the sense of Article 26 GDPR; instead, the system is fashioned by the individual behaviour of the nodes.[9] While the interaction of many nodes powers a blockchain, the modalities of data processing are not determined by the nodes. Additionally, it is challenging to determine the exact number, location, and identity of nodes in a chain. Thus, nodes cannot be joint controllers as they do not jointly determine the purposes and means of the processing.

Another approach to the issue regards the responsibility of the developers. While this perspective has been discussed occasionally in the literature, the typical approach is that developers should not be held responsible under the GDPR or systematically qualify as data controllers. Shellekens argues that core developers decide on the content of the protocol and cannot determine whether the network will utilise it in the way they developed it. To put it differently, while developers establish the protocol, it is up to a group of nodes to decide which version to implement, shaping the reasons behind it 'how'. [24] Following the same logic, some scholars argue that developers could not qualify as controllers.[16] The primary rationale for such an interpretation is that developers usually receive commands from a superior entity, such as their employer company. Therefore, an initial code or protocol developer is generally not regarded as a data controller. However, other interpretations exist. For example, the CNIL is of the view that competent contract developers should be considered data controllers when they play a role in the processing [25], [26].

2.4.1.2 AUTHORITATIVE GUIDANCE

The EDPB acknowledges that participants are not on equal footing when it comes to roles and responsibilities; their roles and responsibilities typically depend on the governance model. In permissionless blockchains, nodes can significantly influence processing purposes and essential means (e.g., deciding whether to fork). When nodes pursue their own purposes without following a controller's directives, the EDPB strongly advocates for creating a consortium or another form of legal entity among the nodes. This off-chain legal structure, known as the consortium, would serve as the controller for processing. [27]

(II) THE RIGHT TO ERASURE AND RELEVANT ISSUES

Article 17 GDPR: The data subject shall have the right to obtain from the controller the erasure of personal data concerning him or her without undue delay and the controller shall have the obligation to erase personal data without undue delay [...]

In public blockchains, the data becomes immutable once registered into the blocks, as it is nearly impossible to change a block without altering the subsequent blocks. [28] In practice, erasure or modification is not viable because public blockchain networks comprise numerous "nodes" worldwide. The issue is technical rather than a conceptual one. In fact, blocks are not immutable, but it is very difficult to make any modifications in the chain as the blocks are hashed to each other, and any modification requires a decision by the majority of the nodes.[29]

It should be noted that, according to Article 17(2), conditions for erasure must be met to invoke this right. These include data no longer being necessary, withdrawal of consent, unlawful processing, and compliance with legal obligations. Moreover, the right to erasure does not apply if processing is necessary for legal obligations, public health, or legal claims.

The EU's interpretations of the term 'erasure' are divergent. When analysing the use case, we will discuss these interpretations, authoritative opinions, and suggestions in Part II in detail. For now, some prominent technical measures suggested can be mentioned, although some have already become obsolete. For example, the techniques explained by Article 29 WP, such as the destruction of the hardware or overwriting of data, can be considered outdated in the context of blockchains.[30] The CNIL (French Data Protection Authority) is of the view that the erasure of the private key would suffice to achieve the erasure of personal data on blockchains.[25] This makes it impossible to make a transaction, or in the case where the transaction is received, decryption is not possible without the private key. However, this does not delete the data stored in the chain; public keys and other transaction data remain. As mentioned, the data stored in the chain (usually the public key addresses) is considered pseudonymous and thus still falls under the material scope of the GDPR. On the other hand, this method can be considered rather data-protection friendly, as it would allow the control to remove the linkability of the blockchain that points to the off-chain data.

German data protection legislation has an interesting approach to the issue. Section 35(1) provides that data subjects do not have a right to erasure in the case of *non-automated* processing where the erasure would not be possible or involve a disproportionate effort due to the type of storage.²⁵ However, the main focus of this provision is non-automated processing, unlike blockchain-based processing of data, which is considered automated.²⁶ [31]

The literature, in particular technical literature, suggested several options, such as the complete deletion of any off-chain data, which is the most common suggestion for the implementation of the right to erasure.[32], [33], [34], [35] In these types of solutions, personal data is stored in off-chain repositories, with the blockchain retaining only a hash value that links to the storage location of this data. When an individual requests the deletion of their personal data, the information stored in the off-chain repository can be permanently removed. Consequently, the hash value on the blockchain, which previously referenced the now-deleted data, becomes ineffective and loses its function. This technique can be strengthened by using other technical solutions, such as smart contracts. We will focus on this technical option — and its pros and cons — in Part II, considering the specifics of our use case.

To ensure data minimisation, many technical suggestions have been made by scholars. These include hashing out, zero-knowledge proof (ZKP),[36] ring signatures,[37] secure-multi party computation [38] and so on... However, these solutions remain unclear as to whether they can ensure anonymisation in terms of the GDPR's high thresholds.

2.5 OTHER RELEVANT EU LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The European Union's data strategy aims to promote wider availability and use of data to stimulate economic growth, improve public services, and enhance transparency.[39] The strategy includes revisions to the Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive²⁷ and expanding the scope of the Open Data Directive, integrating it into a broader open data policy.[40] The Data Strategy introduces new regulatory elements, such as the Data Governance Act and Data Act, which attempt to balance creating market-based mechanisms for data sharing with respecting privacy rights and promoting alternative data governance models. These efforts are part of the EU's goal to become a leading role model for a data-empowered society, fostering better decision-making in both business and public sectors. [41]

²⁵ (BDSG 35(1)), German Data Protection Regulation, Translations provided by the Language Service of the Federal Ministry of the Interior at https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_bdsdg/

²⁶ "Blockchain is not an automatic but an automated system."

²⁷ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information

2.5.1 OPEN DATA DIRECTIVE

As part of the European Strategy for Data, the Open Data Directive serves as a common legal framework for data held by the government, also known as public sector information. This directive supports two fundamental principles within the European market: transparency and fair competition. By promoting open access to government-held data, the directive aims to enhance transparency in public administration and create a level playing field for businesses, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), by enabling equal access to valuable public data.[42]

2.5.2 DATA GOVERNANCE ACT

The Data Governance Act (DGA) aims to set the conditions for enhancing the development of the common European data spaces, as identified in the strategy document, by bringing trust in data sharing and data intermediaries. Towards that aim, the DGA lays down an overarching framework comprising horizontal measures relevant to all common European data spaces. The Regulation entered into force in June 2022 and is applicable since September 2023.

The Regulation legislates a new model for data sharing by introducing two new types of services. Firstly, it regulates "data intermediation services", i.e. services that will act as market facilitators, enabling transactions between data holders and data users. The Regulation imposes a stringent neutrality obligation on these services concerning the data exchanged, ensuring fair, transparent and non-discriminatory access to their services. Secondly, it regulates so-called "data altruism" organisations. These are non-profit organisations that gather data either shared directly by individuals and companies or indirectly collected by others, voluntarily and without reward, to be used for objectives of general interest (such as health research or mobility). The aim is to support the emergence of EU-wide data pools made available based on data altruism to enable data analytics and machine learning.

The DGA does not directly impact blockchain, but it remains to be seen whether the aforementioned intermediary services will deploy blockchain to record and execute data transactions securely.

2.5.3 DATA ACT

The second most crucial legislative initiative under the 2020 Data Strategy is the Data Act ("DA"). Its aim is to encourage and enable greater and fairer B2B and B2G data access and use in all sectors. First, in terms of B2B data use, the DA provides data access rules for users (and third parties at the users' request) of IoT products or related services (Chapter II). Second, Chapter III creates a *lex generalis* for data-sharing obligations provided under existing horizontal or sector-specific legislation. There is a direct – although implicit – connection with data spaces, for which more specific data-sharing obligations could be laid down in the future. Third, the Act harmonises the rules to prevent the exploitation of contractual imbalances between businesses by mainstreaming the principle of fairness in B2B commercial data transactions. However, only to the benefit of SMEs, which significantly reduces the scope of application (Chapter IV), facilitates switching between data processing services (Chapter VI) and enhances interoperability (Chapter VIII).

A "data processing service" is defined in Article 2 and Recital 80 as a digital service provided to a customer that enables ubiquitous and on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable, scalable, and elastic computing resources of a centralised, distributed, or highly distributed nature. This definition may apply to both blockchains and cloud platforms, as analysed below.

In the context of boosting interoperability, the DA also regulates smart contracts. The DA defines smart contracts as *"a computer program used for the automated execution of an agreement or part thereof, using a sequence of electronic data records and ensuring their integrity and the accuracy*

of their chronological ordering”²⁸ The definition is considered technologically neutral and can capture smart contracts whether connected to an electronic ledger or not, but it excludes smart contracts deployed for internal in-house use. [43] However, the DA specifies that the smart contract provisions only apply to smart contracts that are deployed in the context of executing an agreement, or part of it, to make data available. Therefore, the existence of an off-chain agreement becomes a prerequisite for the DA provisions to apply.

Indeed, the DA obliges the vendor of an application using smart contracts, or a professional who deploys smart contracts commercially for third parties in the context of executing a data-sharing agreement, to comply with the following “essential” requirements: ⁵

- Robustness and access control to avoid functional errors and third-party manipulation. This requirement aims to address bugs and external influences that have been identified as challenges in smart contract deployment.[43]²⁹
- Safe termination and interruption. A mechanism must exist to stop ongoing transactions, with internal functions to reset or interrupt the contract, preventing future issue executions.³⁰ This requirement, Casolari et al. highlight, implies *mutual consent* from the parties to the data sharing agreement, moving beyond the inherent unamendability of traditional smart contracts.[43]
- Data archiving and continuity, saving transactional data and the logic and code used for the smart contract. In cases where a smart contract must be terminated or deactivated, there must be a way to archive the transactional data, smart contract logic, and code. This provision aims to ensure “auditability” by preserving a record of past operations on the data.³¹
- Consistency with the terms of the data-sharing agreement that it executes.
- Once these requirements are fulfilled, an EU declaration of conformity must be issued. Smart contract vendors or deployers must perform a conformity assessment and issue an EU declaration of conformity.³²

Several criticisms could be raised against these provisions.

First, the DA ignores the different types of potential smart contracts. Indeed, smart contracts are not necessarily tied to a traditional legal agreement between two parties. [44]³³ This implies that smart contracts are overly generalised in the legislation. Regarding the scope of the DA, the European Crypto Initiative called for clarity on the question of whether the smart contracts in the DA cover non-blockchain applications.[45]

Secondly, it may disincentivise concluding traditional data-sharing agreements—with the potential to apply smart contracts—to escape the application of the DA and its stringent conditions. This, in turn, may lead to a chilling effect on the deployment of smart contracts.

3 CLOUD PLATFORMS

²⁸ Article 2(39) of the Data Act.

²⁹ Article 36(1)(a) of the Data Act.

³⁰ Article 36(1)(b) of the Data Act.

³¹ Article 36(1)(c)(d)(e) of the Data Act

³² Article 36 (2)(3) of the Data Act.

³³ Principle 2. p.22.

This section provides an overview of the technical aspects and the regulatory framework applicable to cloud platforms.

3.1.1 TECHNICAL OVERVIEW

Cloud computing, commonly referred to as a "cloud platform" in a broader context, is essentially the provision of computing resources over the Internet. Cloud platforms enable "on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources".^[46] These resources encompass networks, servers, storage, applications, and services, all crafted for quick provisioning and release with minimal management or service provider involvement. ^[46]

There are three service models that are commonly used, known as:

(i) Software as a Service (SaaS): enables cloud customers to directly access and use software applications like ERP, CRM, and social networks that run on a computing architecture entirely managed by the cloud provider.^[47]

ii) Platform as a Service (PaaS); The provider offers a platform layer that includes hardware and software components, allowing customers to install, develop, or run their applications without handling the underlying infrastructure.^[48]

(iii) Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS): This model involves the provider supplying basic computing resources and hardware infrastructure as an online service within a virtualised environment, e.g., virtual machines, storage and networking.^[46]

The deployment of cloud platforms has five models: private, community, public and hybrid.³⁴ In addition, Multi-Tenant Cloud Platforms are gaining popularity. In MTC, the cloud architecture is shared by multiple customers, meaning that they share the same computing resources, but their data is logically isolated. ^[49]

3.1.2 REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

Cloud platforms are subject to a complex and evolving regulatory framework, primarily driven by data protection and intellectual property laws. As the main legal framework regarding blockchain technology, which was analysed above, also applies to cloud platforms, we will not repeat those in this section. We will refer to such a framework in the section title "Legal Challenges related to Cloud Platforms" where relevant.

3.1.2.1 THE NIS2 DIRECTIVE

The NIS2 Directive is worth mentioning for cloud platforms, as it imposes security and notification requirements on essential services, including cloud computing services. The NIS2 came into force in 2023 to address increasing digitisation and evolving cybersecurity threats. The Directive applies to public or private entities of a type referred to in Annex I or Annex II, which usually exceed the ceilings for medium-sized enterprises. Under this Directive, EU Member States are mandated to enforce cybersecurity risk management responsibilities on essential and important entities, including providers of cloud computing services.³⁵ Although both categories aim to meet the

³⁵ Article 21 of the NIS2 Directive.

Directive's goal of a high common level of cybersecurity, the respective obligations are similar for these two categories; essential entities have a stricter supervisory and enforcement regime and greater potential penalties for non-compliance.³⁶

"Cloud computing service providers" are explicitly listed under "Digital infrastructure" in Annex I of the Directive, which is titled "SECTORS OF HIGH CRITICALITY." If a cloud computing service provider falls within the general scope of the Directive (meaning it qualifies as a medium-sized enterprise) but does not exceed the ceilings for medium-sized enterprises, it will be considered an important entity. Generally, entities of a type referred to in Annex I (like cloud computing service providers) that qualify as medium-sized enterprises or exceed the ceilings for medium-sized enterprises are considered essential entities. Even if a cloud computing service provider does not meet this threshold, it can still be identified as an essential entity by a Member State, regardless of size. This can be the case if:

- The cloud service provider is the sole provider in a Member State of a service essential for critical societal or economic activities.
- The disruption of the cloud platform could have a significant impact on public safety, security or health or could induce a significant systemic risk, with cross-border impact.
- If the cloud platform is critical due to its specific significance at the national or regional level, or service type.

Essential entities must take appropriate and proportionate technical, operational, and organisational measures to manage risks to their network and information systems. These measures should prevent or minimise the impact of incidents on service recipients and other services, considering the state-of-the-art, relevant European and international standards, and implementation costs. Proportionality should consider the entity's risk exposure, size, likelihood of incidents, and their societal and economic impact.³⁷

These measures must be based on an all-hazards approach and include at least the following:³⁸

- Policies on risk analysis and information system security
- Incident handling
- Business continuity
- Supply chain security
- Security in network and information systems acquisition, development, and maintenance
- Policies and procedures to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity risk-management measures
- Basic cyber hygiene practices and cybersecurity training
- Policies and procedures regarding the use of cryptography and, where appropriate, encryption
- Human resources security, access control policies, and asset management
- The use of multi-factor authentication or continuous authentication solutions, secured voice, video, and text communications, and secured emergency communication systems within the entity, where appropriate.

These cybersecurity risk-management measures must also address the physical and environmental security of network and information systems by including protection against system failures, human error, malicious acts, or natural phenomena, consistent with European and international standards, such as the ISO/IEC 27000 series.³⁹ It is worth noting that this legislation applies to both personal and non-personal data.

³⁶ Recital 15 of the NIS2 Directive.

³⁷ Article 21(2) of the NIS2 Directive.

³⁸ Article 21(2) (e-j) of the NIS2 Directive.

³⁹ Recital 79 of the NIS2 Directive.

3.1.2.2 DATA ACT

As mentioned, the Data Act applies to cloud platforms under the general category of “data processing services”.⁴⁰ Data processing services encompass various service models, including IaaS, PaaS and SaaS, as well as emerging models such as Storage as a Service and Database as a Service.⁴¹

The Data Act also creates new obligations for cloud providers. Cloud providers must take measures to enable customers to switch to a different provider of the same service type or to an on-premises ICT infrastructure, or to use several providers simultaneously. This includes removing pre-commercial, commercial, technical, contractual, and organisational obstacles that inhibit customers from terminating contracts, concluding new contracts, porting data and digital assets, achieving functional equivalence, and unbundling services.⁴² Providers of Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) must take all reasonable measures to facilitate functional equivalence for the customer after switching. This includes providing capabilities, information, documentation, and tools.⁴³

Notably, in business-to-business relations, where the user of a connected product or related service is an enterprise (and not the data subject), “the user is considered to be a controller”⁴⁴. Where the data holder and the user are “joint controllers” within the meaning of GDPR Article 26, they must define their respective responsibilities.

3.1.3 LEGAL CHALLENGES RELATED TO CLOUD PLATFORMS

The legal issues in cloud computing centre on data protection, accountability, security, intellectual property and trade secret protection.

3.1.3.1 DATA PROTECTION ACCOUNTABILITY

When several actors have influence and responsibility over the software and storage, accountability becomes a critical issue. Cloud controllers and processors based in the EU must comply with GDPR requirements. Additionally, non-EU cloud services must comply with the GDPR if they offer services to EU citizens or conduct monitoring activities within the EU.

However, the research shows that there are accountability issues in cloud platforms. Kamarinou et al. (2015) find, through empirical analysis of cloud service provider policies, that many providers’ terms of service and privacy policies do not align with data protection rights, leading to transparency and redress issues for users.[50]

Furthermore, identifying accountable actors in complex cloud infrastructures is not straightforward. In 2012, the Article 29 Working Party issued an opinion on Cloud Computing, viewing cloud providers as processors and cloud customers as data controllers.[51] This can also be observed as the prevailing view in the literature. [52] However, there are strong arguments against this prevailing view that should be taken into consideration.[48]

⁴⁰ See Article 2(8) Definition of Data Processing Service: *a digital service provided to a customer that enables ubiquitous and on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable, scalable and elastic computing resources of a centralised, distributed or highly distributed nature*, and Recital 80 of the Data Act (Explanation of Data Processing Services).

⁴¹ Recital 81 of the Data Act.

⁴² Article 23 of the Data Act.

⁴³ Recital 86 of the Data Act.

⁴⁴ Recital 34 of the Data Act.

In our view, the controller assessment should consider various models and storage strategies within a cloud platform. For instance, in the IaaS model, the provider offers infrastructure as a service to a customer. The service includes hardware, memory, network, and storage.[47] In the PaaS model, the provider provides the essential components of hardware and software that enable customers to develop or run applications.

In the SaaS model, the provider offers almost all components, and customers simply access and use the applications on the platform. Karatas and others state that SaaS is used alongside a storage strategy that allows for shared software and databases, enabling the realisation of multi-tenancy in the cloud. [49] As almost all means of processing are determined by the cloud provider, in the SaaS model, the cloud provider's factual influence on processing is highly similar to that of the data controller.[48] In other words, '*... identifying the entity displaying the concrete ability to protect the personal data of data subjects and take preventive actions against potential infringements would bright the qualification of the cloud actors in line with the literal, historic and teleological interpretation of the controller concept.*'[48]

3.1.3.2 CYBERSECURITY

Ensuring the security and integrity of personal data in the cloud is a primary concern in data protection. This is especially vital when third-party multi-tenant cloud service providers host applications and their data. When storing data in the cloud, it is crucial to implement robust security measures to prevent unauthorised access. Ensuring that the data remains secure and inaccessible to the public or any malicious tenants is imperative. [53]

Article 51 of the Cyber Security Act (CSA) provides the security objectives of the CS certification:⁴⁵ To ensure comprehensive data protection throughout the entire lifecycle of ICT products, services, or processes, it is crucial to safeguard data against accidental or unauthorised access, processing, storage, and disclosure. This includes protecting data from destruction, loss, alteration and ensuring availability. Access controls must ensure that only authorised entities can access specific data, services, or functions. Dependencies and vulnerabilities should be identified and documented. Access and usage records must be maintained and verifiable to monitor who accessed data and when. Additionally, ICT products, services, and processes should be designed and maintained to be secure by default, incorporating up-to-date software and hardware, free from known vulnerabilities, and equipped with mechanisms for secure updates. Finally, timely restoration of data and services must be ensured in case of incidents.⁴⁶

Various solutions have been developed to address these challenges, including access control mechanisms [54] and encryption techniques.[55] Several projects have been undertaken to meet the security requirements. For example, the MOZAIK project has documented crucial aspects of scalable and secure data sharing based on cloud platforms.[53], [56]⁴⁷ Within MOZAIK, Abidin and others provided an analysis of the legal requirements divided into three main categories: (i) secure data collection, (ii) secure data storage, and (iii) secure data processing and sharing.[53] While secure collection in this project primarily concerns Internet of Things (IoT) devices, the second and third categories are relevant to cloud computing. Nonetheless, the secure collection of personal data and secure access control are among the key issues that must be considered in compliance with GDPR

⁴⁵ CSA gives mandates to ENISA to carry out tasks related to cybersecurity in the EU and to set out measures for a better harmonisation within the EU (Article 3 CSA). In this regard, ENISA reports and guidelines are particularly important for cloud service developers and providers to align with the CSA and further the GDPR's security requirements, as they are interlinked.

⁴⁶ The requirements defined in the EUCS scheme are derived from various existing standards and conformity assessment schemes. These requirements encompass all categories defined in information security standards, such as ISO 27001. ENISA, 'EUCS – Cloud Services Scheme' (www.enisa.europa.eu 22 December 2022) <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/eucs-cloud-service-scheme>, 33.

⁴⁷ MOZAIK, 'MOZAIK: Scalable and Secure Data Sharing' (Mozaik) <<https://www.esat.kuleuven.be/cosic/projects/mozaik/>> accessed 23 June 2024

principles, such as accuracy. To ensure secure IoT-to-cloud processing, the data collected by an IoT device should be encrypted and remain encrypted when stored in the cloud, preventing any meaningful data from being revealed to other entities in the system.[56]

Finally, Gupta and others observe that no single method can ensure absolute data security for all participants in the system, whether directly or indirectly involved. Achieving comprehensive security requires combining various techniques to provide complete protection in a data-sharing environment.[57]

3.1.3.3 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RELATED LEGAL ISSUES

IP rights and trade secrets are also mentioned as other challenges. For instance, database rights in the EU are a unique right that is noted as a challenge to traditional IP frameworks in cloud platforms and big data contexts.[58] Cloud platforms and big data analytics often rely on aggregating and sharing massive datasets, where database rights enshrined in the Database Directive (Directive 96/9/EC) restrict the re-use of data, which challenges integration with data sharing platforms such as data spaces.[59]

Regarding this, the Data Act states that data obtained from connected products and related services do not qualify for sui generis database right.⁴⁸ Cloud providers, as data holders, must ensure users have timely access to readily available data and relevant metadata and facilitate sharing with third parties. This means that cloud providers can no longer use sui generis rights as a justification for not sharing data.

⁴⁸ Article 43 of the Data Act.

PART II: DATA PROTECTION USE CASE ASSESSMENT

The previous Part of the deliverable focused on blockchain technology and cloud in isolation and generally provided an applicable legal framework. To analyse the data protection risks, we present a specific case study here that utilises blockchain technology in conjunction with cloud solutions to process data. A case study was developed specifically to demonstrate the risks associated with sensitive data in a large-scale emergency response scenario, which is use case #3 of NOUS.

Large-scale emergency responses, undertaken by firefighters, civil security, and law enforcement organisations alike, require advanced operational command capabilities, along with clear situational awareness shared in real-time, by all involved parties, from the local or regional level up to the highest level of government in the event of a significant escalation.

1. HYPOTHETICAL CASE STUDY: FIRE AT A LARGE URBAN STADIUM DURING A MAJOR EVENT

During a sold-out Taylor Swift concert at a large urban stadium, a fire breaks out in one of the concession areas, quickly spreading to nearby sections due to flammable materials stored in the vicinity. The stadium, packed with tens of thousands of attendees, is at risk of a catastrophic event if the fire is not contained and the audience safely evacuated.

As the fire rapidly grows, stadium security initiates an emergency evacuation, but the scale of the event and the dense crowd lead to chaos and potential stampede risks. Local fire departments, emergency medical services (EMS), and law enforcement are immediately alerted. Given the complexity of the situation, Altrex software, enhanced with blockchain technology, is deployed to coordinate the multi-agency response, involving fire departments, EMS, police, and stadium security.

Each employee's access to the system is logged on the blockchain, with their log-in details, role, and actions recorded. The blockchain logs every instance of access by responders to the Altrex system, creating a tamper-proof record of who accessed what data and when. This includes log-in times, the information retrieved, and any actions taken. All activities, including the handling of video footage and employee access data, are recorded on the blockchain. This level of detail is crucial for accountability and later audits.

The platform manages video feeds from stadium cameras, body cams of responders, and drones used to monitor the situation. This data is essential for monitoring evacuation progress and identifying potential hazards. These video feeds capture images and movements of thousands of attendees.

Altrex facilitates secure data sharing with external agencies, such as additional fire departments or forensic teams, by using blockchain technology to protect the integrity of video footage and employee data.

Altrex software integrates geospatial data, including real-time satellite imagery and digital twin models of the stadium, to create a detailed map of the incident site. This map includes information on the exact location of the affected areas, the spread of the fire, and the proximity of the fire to vital infrastructure, such as storage tanks, warehouses, and residential areas nearby. Live weather data, including wind speed and direction, is also incorporated into the system to predict the movement of the fire and inform evacuation and containment strategies.

Additionally, it integrates geospatial data to provide a comprehensive view of the situation. This includes mapping the locations of affected individuals in real-time, helping to ensure that all are accounted for and that high-risk areas are prioritised for evacuation.

Drones equipped with cameras and sensors are deployed to monitor the spread of the fire and track the movements of individuals in the affected areas. These drones capture real-time video and environmental data, which are linked to the personal data of those exposed, allowing for precise tracking and monitoring of potential health impacts.

Sensors placed around the stadium collect air quality data, which is matched with the geolocation data of nearby individuals to assess their exposure levels to smoke and determine immediate medical needs. The data collected during the evacuation is securely stored in Altrex, with access restricted to authorised personnel to protect the privacy of the evacuees. Moreover, these data are encrypted and recorded on a blockchain. The blockchain also tracks the provenance of this data, providing a clear audit trail of how and when it was collected.

Altrex software is designed for crisis management during disasters, industrial accidents, and terrorism-related incidents. The platform is built to facilitate communication and coordination between various organisations involved in crisis management. These include emergency services, law enforcement, and other tactical units. Altrex enables these agencies to exchange critical information, such as situational reports, commands, and multimedia data (e.g., pictures, videos, and audio recordings), which are essential for informed decision-making during crises. For example, the platform utilises common alert protocols that enable it to integrate with existing systems used by agencies, such as those employed by firefighters in France, ensuring that all parties can work together effectively.

The software integrates a combination of geospatial and situational data, which is processed and displayed on edge devices and central servers. These systems handle a wide variety of sensitive data, including live sensor feeds, video streams from drones, geolocation data, and other situational information crucial for decision-making during emergencies.

Altrex software employs a centralised server system that manages storage and access to sensitive data. The platform uses Nginx as a cloud component for sharing services, with access management facilitated by software that supports multi-factor authentication. A resource server, as defined by OAuth 2.0, is a server that may accept and respond to requests. Any confidential client application can act as a resource server. The right-to-know management system is to prevent unauthorised access while allowing necessary traceability to uphold legal standards.

The platform uses cloud-based architecture, featuring components such as multi-factor authentication. This architecture ensures that data can be securely shared and accessed across different locations and devices. Most data processing occurs on centralised servers, although some distributed processing capabilities are available, particularly for handling large datasets, such as 3D models and satellite imagery.

Altrex supports video management systems, particularly for handling live streams from drones and other surveillance equipment. This video data is geolocated and can be displayed as icons on maps, allowing operators to track live feeds and analyse the situation in real time. The system also supports the uploading of pictures and videos, which can be crucial for documenting the problem and making informed decisions.

Along with the client components (in the control centre and in the field), the platform enables:

- Dynamic 2D and 3D maps of the territory, with real-time sharing of information on a need-to-know basis and specific symbology for crisis management and symbology specific to emergency plans
- Multi-layer maps of risks, listed establishments, land use, etc.
- Crisis organisation charts and collaborative crisis directories for each municipality

- Checklist and quick reference sheets sorted by category in a document library
- Real-time management and monitoring of the local authority's human and material resources, which are committed, available and can be shared, with GPS location and sectorisation
- Automatic and customisable collaborative log (recording and tracking of actions for after-action review purposes)
- Coordination of emergency resources in collaboration with Altrex-equipped organisations, management and command of operations, monitoring of incidents, and assignment of tasks.
- Integration of video feeds and photos from the field

1.2. PRELIMINARY DATA PROTECTION ANALYSIS

To evaluate the data protection issues related to blockchain and cloud use in this selected use case, we rely on the GDPR's comprehensive accountability framework, prioritising a risk-based approach.⁴⁹

The starting point for this analysis is 'the principle of accountability' under Article 5(2) in the GDPR, which states that data controllers and processors to comply with the principles enshrined in Article 5 – namely transparency, lawfulness, fairness, data minimisation, storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality – and to be able to demonstrate this compliance. Accountability is essential for effective data protection as it underpins and strengthens all other principles in this domain. One of the main aspects of accountability under the GDPR is the demonstration of compliance. The controller must take a proactive role in ensuring that data protection obligations are met by technical and organisational methods, as well as be able to demonstrate compliance.

Table 1: Table showing the categories of personal data, purposes and storage

<i>Category of Personal Data</i>	<i>Use/Purpose</i>	<i>Collection Method</i>	<i>Storage and Deletion</i>	<i>Transfer</i>
Images of natural persons	Monitoring / facilitating the evacuation process	Drones, CCTV, body cams, satellite	Centralised server and cloud; retained for a limited time unless legally required	Shared with emergency services and relevant authorities
Movements of natural persons	To avert further risks of a stampede	Drones, CCTV, body cams, satellite	Centralised server and cloud; deleted after incident resolution unless needed for investigations	Shared with coordination teams and public safety authorities
Employee access data, incl. metadata	Secure access to Altrex, access to sensitive data	Altrex software on local devices	Stored on centralised server and blockchain; subject to access logs and retention policy	Internal transfers within organisation and potentially auditors
Employee communication data	To coordinate teams for crisis management	Altrex software on local devices	Centralised server and blockchain; retained per internal policy or for audits	Internal transfer; shared with crisis management teams
Personal data of criminal suspects / Medical data	Crime investigation / judicial and emergency medical purposes	Police reports, field devices, body cams, medical staff input	Secured judicial or medical data systems; retention per legal requirements (e.g., Code of Criminal Procedure, medical record rules)	Transferred to law enforcement, judiciary, and medical services as permitted by law

⁴⁹ For an introduction to accountability principle, see Part I Section 3 on the Legal Challenges of Cloud Computing.

Figure 1: Basic data flow diagram of the case study

The system processes large volumes of highly sensitive data, including real-time geospatial information, video footage, and personal data related to crisis management operations. This includes data from various sources like edge devices, legacy systems, sensor networks, and drones. The combination of live sensor data, such as earth observation and weather probes, with tactical information exchanged between multiple organisations (e.g., reports, pictures, videos, and audio recordings) introduces significant risks concerning data privacy and protection.

The platform draws data from various sources, including legacy systems, sensor networks, drones, and geolocation tools. For instance, live sensor data, such as weather probes and earth observation imagery, can be integrated with 3D terrain models and Building Information Models (BIM) to create a "digital twin" of the crisis environment. This digital twin provides a highly accurate, real-time representation of the physical space, aiding in planning and response efforts.

The platform's connection to law enforcement agencies and interoperability with various organisations using common alert protocols are critical. While this enhances the utility of the software in crisis scenarios, it also introduces vulnerabilities related to data exchange between systems. Ensuring secure and controlled communication channels is essential to prevent data breaches and unauthorised data sharing.

The Altrex software predominantly relies on a centralised server for data processing and storage, with some components distributed across different environments. This reliance on centralised systems for storing and processing vast amounts of data, including 3D models, satellite exchanges, and live sensor data, increases the risk of data breaches. Distributed processing capabilities, while present, need to be assessed to ensure they do not introduce additional risks, particularly in relation to data redundancy and synchronisation.

In any personal data processing operation, a clear description of who is processing and accessing the data is crucial. The system supports a "need-to-know" basis for information sharing, meaning that only the necessary data is accessible to specific users, enhancing both operational efficiency

and security. However, as explained in Part I, there is currently no clarity on who determines the means and purposes of the processing in public blockchains. Therefore, this can be considered one of the risks associated with this specific use case.

Another essential point to consider is the data retention periods. As mentioned previously, any data that is verified and stored on a blockchain is very difficult to alter. This is a significant issue when it comes to the necessity test, as the least intrusive measures should be opted for in the processing. When coupled with a PKI system, the encrypted data is time-stamped, which makes it almost impossible to change. The technology enables real-time auditing and verification of data at minimal cost, making it economically viable for large-scale implementations.[60] As changes in the datasets can be detected, research shows that a particular deployment of blockchain limits fraud for the time being. Technology proves necessary in contexts where the integrity of data is in demand, such as access control to sensitive data.

1.3. NECESSITY TEST

Any measure involving the processing of personal data is considered an interference with the right to personal data under Article 52(1) of the Charter. Pursuant to this Article, the limitation on a fundamental right should respect the essence of the right, meaning that the limitation shall not empty the right of its core elements and prevent the exercise of the right. Furthermore, the limitations must be provided by law, genuinely meet the objectives of general interest recognised by the Union, or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others, and must be necessary and proportionate.

The term "necessary" as defined in the context of Article 10(2) of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) (referred to in the GDPR context) implies the existence of a "pressing social need," going beyond mere "admissible," "ordinary," "useful," "reasonable," or "desirable" qualities. The necessity test requires "a combined, fact-based assessment of the effectiveness of the measure for the objective pursued and of whether it is less intrusive compared to other options for achieving the same goal." [61]

To conduct the test correctly, EDPS emphasises that it is crucial to have a clear and well-defined purpose for the processing in question. Hence, the preliminary first step requires 'a detailed factual description' of the measure (interference) and its purpose. [61] This assessment of necessity and proportionality (as discussed below) is a key part of the DPIA outlined in Article 35 of the GDPR.

The purposes of the processing operations can be documented as:

- (i) Crisis management
- (ii) Protect the lives and well-being of society
- (iii) Facilitate evacuation
- (iv) Prevent secondary incidents
- (v) Evidence for law enforcement
- (vi) Comply with legal obligations: Stadium operators and emergency response teams are often legally obligated to collect and process personal data during an emergency to comply with safety regulations and reporting requirements.
- (vii) Post-incident analysis: It is critical to analyse the incident to understand what went well and what could be improved for future emergencies
- (viii) Transparency of the processing: Processing personal data, such as employee log-in details and access records, ensures that there is a clear, tamper-proof record of who did what, when, and why. This data is crucial for holding individuals and organisations accountable for their actions and ensuring that all steps taken during the incident were appropriate and justified.

The necessity test includes the description of the objective of general interest.^[61] The general interest here can be defined as the protection of human health and the prevention of crisis management. As mentioned previously, these interests can even be interpreted to ensure public security. The urgent nature of a fire emergency necessitates the rapid processing of certain personal data to save lives and prevent harm.

To assess the necessity, the categories of data must be clearly identified prior to processing. As there are no concrete purposes given, an ill-defined interference can affect the lawfulness of the limitation and would further prevent the clarification of the other rights at stake. According to the jurisdiction of the CJEU, it does not matter whether the data is sensitive.⁵⁰ Each processing operation, e.g. collection, storage, and access, should be considered as a separate interference (or limitation) and its necessity should be assessed individually and cumulatively. To do so, each processing and each category of data should be clearly defined.

When it comes to blockchain data processing, the EDPB emphasises the importance of assessing the necessity of using the technology for processing personal data. The choice of blockchain technology must comply with the necessity principle; it is crucial to document why the technology has been chosen for a particular processing activity.^[27] Given the sensitive nature of the data handled by Altrex, the platform includes features designed to ensure legal compliance. For example, the software logs all activities, providing a verifiable record of events that can be used as legal proof. This is particularly important in scenarios where the data might be used in judicial proceedings or to verify the presence of personnel in specific locations.

The judicialisation of incidents handled by Altrex software implies that the data must be tamper-proof and reliable for legal proceedings. There are concerns regarding the accuracy and integrity of the data, especially in scenarios where information is entered incorrectly or deliberately altered. The system's logs, which serve as legal proof (e.g., confirming that a person was in a specific location), must be secure and verifiable. The platform's ability to log all actions and provide legal proof of events ensures that the response is not only effective but also fully documented, which is crucial for post-crisis analysis and legal accountability.

However, public blockchains should only be used if public access to the data on the blockchain is necessary for at least one of the processing purposes (discussed above). ^[27] In addition, measures should be taken to limit the accessibility of personal data to what is necessary for each specific purpose.^[27] This means that storing personal data on-chain in a directly identifying form on a public blockchain is only justified by the purpose of the processing.

It is worth noting that current blockchain applications often lack sufficient scalability for storing large volumes of data, such as video, voice, or high-resolution images. Thus, most scalable solutions are typically off-chain or hybrid models that store larger files in IPFS (InterPlanetary File System) or Cloud/edge services. Altrex can integrate blockchain technology (at the time of writing this deliverable) to store video from drones in IPFS, writing the hash file of each file, along with its timestamp, on-chain to prove that it has not been tampered with. In other words, blockchain technology can be helpful for verifying and timestamping large files, but it is not directly designed for storing them. ^{[62], [63]} As this bottleneck can be eliminated in the future, the analysis below considers both possibilities: initially, processed data is stored on the blockchain, and only metadata is stored on the blockchain.

⁵⁰ CJEU, Cases C-465/00, C-138/01 and C-139/01 *Österreichischer Rundfunk and Others*, paragraph 75 and *Digital Rights Ireland*, paragraph 33

1.4. PROPORTIONALITY

In some cases, it is possible that *legitimate interests* of the controller might conflict with the right to the protection of personal data. Such interests can belong to third parties and stem from other fundamental rights. If such conflict is inevitable, to mitigate potential risks and not to harm the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals, the principle of proportionality must be applied.

The principle requires that:⁵¹

- The measures taken shall not “exceed the limits of what is appropriate and necessary in order to attain the objectives legitimately pursued by the legislation in question”.
- If “there is a choice between several appropriate measures, “the least onerous” one shall be chosen.
- The harm caused “must not be disproportionate to the aims pursued” by the legislation.
- Proportionality requires that the inferences with the right to personal data protection are appropriate and necessary to achieve legitimate objectives. To implement these principles, data controllers shall *strike a balance* between the *means and objectives* of the processing.
- Benefits of the processing: the social and economic benefits of the processing are multifold. It is beneficial for the controller(s) as the processing is likely to lead to better evaluations and tactics.

The technology used is relatively new, so it may be prone to errors, which could lead to unfair decisions or similar legal consequences affecting the freedoms and rights of data subjects.

In 2014, the Article 29 WP provided guidelines for the proportionality test in its opinion on the notion of legitimate interests. Pursuant to the interpretation of the Article 29 WP, before applying the balancing test, both legitimate interests of the controller and its impact on the interests and rights of the data subject should be pictured on a spectrum.[64] Based on this evaluation, legitimate interests can range from insignificant to compelling. On the other hand, the impact of legitimate interests on the freedoms and rights of data subjects can range from trivial to very serious. Once the weight of both sides has been evaluated, it is necessary to assess whether the legitimate interests of the controller or a third party outweigh the interests and rights of the data subject. It is crucial to determine if the nature and scope of the controller's legitimate interests are both necessary and proportionate. Based on this initial assessment, a “provisional balance” can be established. However, in many cases, the outcome of this provisional balance test may remain uncertain. If the initial balancing test yields an unclear result, legal experts should then examine whether additional safeguards are in place to ensure the protection of the data subject's rights.[65] Additional safeguards can significantly tip the balance in favour of the controller.[64]

2. PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT OF RISKS, INCLUDING FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS

The concept of risk is central to the GDPR, especially under the principle of accountability. Risk is not just about compliance; it plays a crucial role in ensuring the protection of the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals. This involves not only the rights to data protection, but also broader rights impacted by data processing activities. GDPR risk assessment does not only refer to the rights enshrined in the GDPR, but all fundamental rights and freedoms, such as privacy, freedom of

⁵¹ See for example: Judgment of the Court of 20 May 2003, Österreichischer Rundfunk Joined Cases C-465/00, C-138/01, EU:C:2003:294, para. 84.

expression, and non-discrimination.[66] Therefore, when assessing the risks related to the processing of personal data, one should take into account the entire fundamental rights framework. Risk assessments should consider both the likelihood and severity of potential harm to these rights.[66] According to the legal scholar *Demetzou*, the scope of the risk should encompass not only the risks to data subjects but also broader societal risks and broader societal harms.[66] Moreover, the risks should be assessed by various stakeholders, including developers and data controllers. This is crucial given the distributed nature of control in complex technological ecosystems, such as in the use case.

It is useful here to differentiate between (i) **employee data** processed during the access to Altrex Software and the usage data, including communication data and (ii) **other natural persons'** data at the stadium, as the risks and safeguards might differ. Some risks, however, are common to both types of personal data processing.

Moreover, we see it appropriate to analyse technology-related risks for the purpose of this deliverable. This is particularly relevant for the application of blockchain technology in conjunction with cloud servers. Hence, after documenting the risks based on the nature of the data processed, technology choices in the project will be assessed separately. As mentioned, blockchain technology is still considered a novel technology, and it is typically used for **large-scale data processing activities**. These two elements alone may lead to additional accountability obligations under the GDPR, such as conducting a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) as required by Article 35. While our primary purpose here is not to conduct a DPIA, we find it suitable to apply DPIA methods to assess risks, as they provide a comprehensive risk assessment methodology.

(Art. 35.1 GDPR) processing, in particular, using new technologies, and considering the nature, scope, context, and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons...

As personal data processing described in the use case contains (i) sensitive, (ii) larger-scale processing, and (iii) use of a new technology, i.e., blockchain, it is considered a high-risk processing. Furthermore, the EDPB, in its opinion about DPIA in France, is of the view that **employee monitoring** and **location data processing** require DPIA.[67] This would also apply to the access control data of the employees.

2.1. ARTICLE 8 OF THE EU CHARTER: THE RIGHT TO THE PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA

Both types of data processing risk violating Article 8 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights: ⁵²Video footage and geolocation data could infringe on this right if not handled with adequate safeguards. The exposure of private actions or distress during the evacuation could cause emotional distress, embarrassment, or harm to individuals' reputations.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the risk of surveillance and monitoring of people in public places, such as in a large stadium, does not automatically lead to a violation of the Charter. However, in principle, the protection of these Articles will be triggered in cases where no adequate controls are exercised over the storage periods and use of data collected.

The risk of surveillance and monitoring of people in public places, such as in a large stadium, does not automatically lead to the violation of the Charter. However, in principle, the protection of these Articles will be triggered in cases where no adequate controls are exercised over the storage periods and use of data collected.

⁵² Also see Article 8 of the European Convention of Human Rights.

South Wales Police Case: The South Wales Police AFR system involved deploying surveillance cameras to gather digital photographs of members of the public and compare these photos to a predetermined police watchlist, which consisted of facial images stored in an existing database.⁵³

AFR was not used as a form of covert surveillance. As mentioned, many times in the Court decision, the case relates to the regulation of surveillance camera systems and ⁵⁴ is concerned with *overt surveillance*.⁵⁵ However, the Court held that “*too much discretion is currently left to individual police officers. It is not clear who can be placed on the watchlist nor is it clear that there are any criteria for determining where AFR can be deployed.*”⁵⁶

2.2. RISK OF FUNCTION CREEP

For both processing categories, there is a risk that personal data might be processed beyond what is necessary or without sufficient oversight, leading to misuse and unauthorised access. **The purpose limitation principle** requires:

GDPR Article 5(1)(b): “[Personal data shall be] collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; [...]”

Any further processing must align with the original purpose or be justified under a different legal basis. Any further use or inference of personal data would be unlawful. In the case at hand, biometric data processing, health data processing, profile creation and behavioural data processing based on the previously collected data for the purposes identified above. would be considered as function creep. For instance, in both categories of personal data processing, there is an inherent risk of biometric data processing for the purpose of confirming the unique identity of a natural person. Biometric data can be extracted from the visual data captured by drones, CCTV or body cams at the stadium. These data can also serve as an authentication method for employees to access Altrex Software. Such visual data can further provide personal data revealing ethnicity or religion, which may be used for discriminatory purposes. As will be discussed under the section of safeguards to mitigate the risks, technical and organisational measures should be taken by the controller to ensure that the data processing does not go beyond the initially determined and informed purpose.

A key issue arises when personal data collected under the GDPR for non-law enforcement purposes is later used by law enforcement. Under GDPR, further processing for a different purpose requires a separate legal basis, which could be the consent of the data subject or a legal obligation under national or EU law. [68] This type of risk is particularly pertinent to the use case at hand, as a fire outbreak at a large stadium can be seen as a national security issue and would be subject to a forensic investigation. Therefore, the data might be further shared with the law enforcement agencies. Without adhering to adequate safeguards, this type of further processing would be considered in breach of the GDPR.

South Wales Police Case: (see previous box for the context) This database was enhanced with additional facial images captured by CCTV cameras when a person passes by the area

⁵³ R v. CC South Wales [2020] EWCA Civ 1058 Case No: C1/2019/2670, <https://www.judiciary.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/R-Bridges-v-CC-South-Wales-ors-Judgment.pdf> Para 9.

⁵⁴ See for example para 8; 41; 109; 114

⁵⁵ “As is common ground, covert surveillance is governed by that legislation [the Regulation of Investigatory Powers Act 2000] and would require authority under the system of warrants created by that Act. Overt surveillance, in contrast, such as AFR Locate (as it was carried out by SWP on the facts of the present case) does not require such authorisation.” Para 64.

⁵⁶ Para 91.

where the camera is operational. From this footage, the software detects faces and isolates them from each other, i.e., face detection. Following that, the software extracts biometric features and stores them with a view to comparing them with the previously formed watchlist.

2.3. UNLAWFUL PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

The data controller should carefully determine the lawfulness of processing, the legal basis, and alignment with the purpose.

Article 6 GDPR: Processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies:

- (a) The data subject has given consent
- (b) Processing is necessary for the performance of a contract
- (c) Processing is necessary for compliance with legal obligation to which the controller is subject
- (d) Processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller
- (e) Processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party.

The GDPR primarily emphasises the need for data processing to comply with legal bases (such as consent, contractual necessity, and legal obligations). In the case at hand, consent or contract-based legal grounds would not be feasible to rely on, as there is a substantial power imbalance between the controller and the data subject. However, processing might be necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller. Moreover, as will be further discussed, processing may be necessary for the purposes of a legitimate interest pursued by the controller or a third party.

Article 8(1) of the LED, 'Member States shall provide for processing to be lawful only if and to what extent that processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out by a competent authority for the [law enforcement] purposes... "

As hinted in the previous subsection (purpose limitation), the processing, regardless of the purpose, falls within the scope of the LED if it is carried out by a competent authority. This can be any public authority competent for the prevention and detection of criminal offences, and so on. Such public authority also covers any other body or entity to which the law of a Member State entrusts the exercise of public authority. For example, the internal security services of the public transport and sports federations are approved for the purpose of providing security at sporting events, etc.) A fire breakout in a large international stadium during a global concert might easily fall under the scope of state security.

The LED legal basis overlaps with GDPR Article 6(1)(d), which allows for the processing of personal data where it is necessary in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller. Thus, the role of the end-user controller of Alex Software is significant in determining the legal basis to rely on.

Processing is necessary for public interest. Article 6 paragraph (d) provides a legal ground that may be used by both the private sector and public institutions,⁵⁷ In such cases, official authority or a public interest task may be vested in the controller. For instance, a bar association may process personal data of its members to carry out disciplinary measures against them.[64] In the private sector, particularly in transport and healthcare, official authorities often outsource tasks related to processing personal data. [64] This legal ground differs from the legal obligation since there is no legal requirement for the controller to act in the sake of public interest.[65]

Legitimate interest. Article 6(1)(f) provides that processing of personal data might be necessary in cases where the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, unless these interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject. The burden of proof will be vested on the controller for its legitimate interest.[69] Pursuant to this, a balancing test, which will be analysed in detail, is required to find out whether the fundamental rights or freedoms of the data subject override so-called legitimate interests of the controller.

3. RISKS RELATED TO BLOCKCHAIN AND CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES USED FOR PROCESSING PERSONAL DATA DURING THE CONCERT

In the envisioned use case involving blockchain and cloud technologies for processing personal data, the data is inherently sensitive due to several interrelated factors. First, the nature of the system may make it difficult to adequately inform data subjects, undermining transparency and compliance with information obligations. Second, the data may include or permit the inference of biometric data—such as facial features captured in footage—potentially triggering stricter regulatory safeguards. Furthermore, other special categories of data might be inferred from the context or content of the recordings, including health, religious, or political information. The risk is heightened when this data is linked to information originally collected for other purposes, such as seat numbers or bank details, thereby increasing the likelihood of unlawful profiling and the repurposing of data beyond its original scope. These concerns underline the critical need for robust data protection measures and purpose limitation principles when deploying such systems.

3.1. STORAGE-RELATED RISKS

Storing data, such as a document or digital art, directly on the blockchain in plain text is feasible, but it can lead to several issues. However, as mentioned in Part I, this would trigger many legal issues. Moreover, as mentioned, blockchain is regarded as a novel technology that processes large-scale personal data. Thus, such processing under the GDPR constitutes an example of high-risk personal data processing that must be handled carefully.

As hinted above, blockchain for data processing can be seen as a typical transaction layer, rather than the main data storage solution. On-chain storage of access logs and metadata, including what has been accessed (e.g., cameras, visuals) and for how long, is preferred over storing raw images captured. Off-chain storage, such as cloud, should be preferred for sensitive data processing.

However, opting for this method should consider the vulnerabilities of centralised domains, and multi-tenant clouds. As mentioned previously, centralised databases are highly vulnerable to data breaches. As will be discussed further in the section 'Measures to Address Risks and

⁵⁷ Rec. 45 GDPR - depending on the Member State law. The Member States, however, are not required to adopt specific laws for each processing activity in isolation; such laws might include several processing activities.

Recommendations', robust and state-of-the-art encryption methods should be used for personal data processing. A blockchain layer can also support these encryption methods to increase the security of access to such data.

The personal data collected can be stored on the blockchain layer in three alternative ways: plain text, encrypted or hashed. According to Finck, all three alternatives would still qualify as personal data under the GDPR. However, some options are more data protection-friendly than others, such as storing personal data off-chain and creating a logical link to a hash pointer in the blockchain layer.[9] For example, video footage collected through drones or CCTV cameras can be encrypted in a secure database, and only access metadata to these data can be recorded on the blockchain layer, including the metadata displaying, e.g., who accessed the videos, when and how long... This brings us to another layer of the evaluation that concerns the processing of personal data of whom has access to stadium data.

4. RISKS SPECIFIC TO EMPLOYEE DATA

4.1. LEGAL BASIS FOR PROCESSING EMPLOYEE DATA

As mentioned above, processing can only be considered lawful if and to the extent that at least one of the legal bases in Article 6(1) is relied on. Otherwise, the data processing would be unlawful at the outset, violating both the GDPR and Article 8 of the Charter.

Article 7 of the GDPR states that consent should be informed, unambiguous, and freely given. In other words, the consent legal basis would not be valid because they are not considered to be free. A significant concern with employees' personal data is that it is not advisable to rely on the consent legal basis due to the employer's hierarchical position. The relationship between the data subject and the controller is that of an employer-employee relationship. There is a lingering question: how much control do the subjects have in such dynamic? In this type of relationship, there is an imbalance of power and data subjects, as employees have minimal control. Therefore, consent cannot be the legal basis on which the controller can rely. This issue is independent of the technology used. Thus, neither blockchain-based nor cloud-based processing consent can be relied upon for employee data.

However, the processing can still be voluntary in some cases. There may be situations where it is possible for the employer to demonstrate that consent is actually freely given in exceptional circumstances, where it will have no adverse consequences whatsoever, whether or not consent is given. [70]

Thus, any employee data shall be processed based on other legal bases outlined in Article 6, such as contractual obligations. As discussed under the necessity and proportionality of the processing, the use of technologies in such processing, e.g., blockchain, should be limited to what is strictly necessary. For this matter, we will further discuss which data minimisation and security measures can be applied to the case at hand.

Article 9 of the GDPR might be relevant to mention here. Some categories of employee data might fall under the special categories of personal data, which are by default prohibited from processing. For instance, a biometric picture of the employee can fall under this provision, not because it would be considered biometric data, but because it might reveal other sensitive categories, such as the ethnicity and religion of the data subject. These categories of data can only be processed based on additional legal bases, such as explicit consent and legal obligation. However, the same considerations regarding consent would also apply here.

Article 9(1) GDPR: *Processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.*

Direct processing of any employee data on blockchain without pseudonymisation is not advised, as will be further discussed below. Moreover, processing special categories of personal data (Article 9(1) or other sensitive data, e.g., vulnerable individuals' personal data) without any security measure, e.g., state-of-the-art encryption techniques, would be highly risky, regardless of the technology in question. Such practices would be subject to heavy fines under the GDPR.

DPA Decision Datatilsynet (Denmark) - Vejen Municipality: *The DPA reported a municipality to the police for inadequate security measures and recommended a fine of €26,800 (DKK 200,000) for not encrypting computers containing personal data of children.*^[71]

4.1.1. ACCESS CONTROL

One crucial risk, related to the confidentiality and integrity of personal data (Article 5 GDPR), concerns who has access to the critical components of the software for the purposes of processing. Access control is a mechanism used to restrict access to data or systems. These are typically a set of rules that specify who, e.g., the controller, the processor or the end-user data subject, has legitimate access to personal data, and under which circumstances.^[72] During enrollment, attributes may be created with a specific value. These attributes are referred to as reference identifiers and are intended to remain constant. Tools, such as reference-identifier generators, can create a new, unique value for a reference identifier.⁵⁸ In order to restrict access control to certain authorised people (employees), the data controller may need to process personal data, such as credentials. A credential is a data structure that binds the digital identity to the system using identifiers. In other words, credentials are the proofs used to access a digital account and can take the form of static passwords, one-time codes, electronic signatures, or biometric data.

GDPR Article 25(1): "The controller shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures for ensuring that, by default, only personal data which are necessary for each specific purpose of the processing are processed. [...] personal data are not made accessible without the individual's intervention to an indefinite number of natural persons."

One of the key elements of any identity management system is access management, which comprises (broadly) two main phases: authentication, e.g., password management, and authorisation (also known as access control). Authentication, as the first phase of access management, regards the "right individuals" as it establishes the identity of one party to another. ^[73]

Insufficient access control mechanisms pose risks, such as identity theft and financial loss, which may entitle individuals to compensation under Article 82 of the GDPR. Eventually, the loss of control over one's data can lead to a lack of trust in the entities responsible for data processing.

⁵⁸ ISO/IEC 24760-1:2019 (EN) IT Security and Privacy- A framework for identity management- Part 1: Terminology and concepts, 3.1.7.

4.1.2. TECHNOLOGIES USED FOR ACCESS CONTROL

Considering the above explanation, the storage of access control data, e.g., credentials, is of paramount importance for compliance with the GDPR. Based on the scenario provided above, there are several locations where the employee's personal data will be stored: centralised servers, cloud, and blockchain. Additionally, employees' credentials can be stored on local devices assigned to them for secure access to the premises and the server.

Both cloud and blockchain technologies pose benefits and risks to the personal data protection of employees. The main legal issue regarding cloud systems is that they are considered a single point of failure. The personal data stored in any centralised server is changeable, suggesting that it can be altered. Most modern access control systems rely on public key infrastructures for security. These consist essentially of the hardware, software, processes, and policies needed to handle public and private keys in an asymmetric cryptography configuration. Centralised, trusted organisations, such as message service providers or certificate authorities, manage traditional PKIs. These middlemen are responsible for issuing, signing, and maintaining the digital certificates that attest to the possession of a public key. Such parties either maintain the safe custody of private keys on their own servers or outsource this task. Therefore, these private keys are subject to the control of outside parties. The arrangement is prone to flaws, including being a single point of failure where, for instance, if the authority's signature keys are compromised, the entire PKI is at risk. Such instances, as seen in the Stuxnet cyberattack, may result in the issuance of false certifications using stolen private keys.[74]

Today, on one end, the centralization in identity management (IdM) continues as the mainstream trend with services that reduce the required credentials (e.g., Apple ID, OAuth 2.0). The models deploying central databases aggregate legal, societal, and ethical concerns. Biometric data are particularly at stake when processed in a centralised manner, as shown by recent history.⁵⁹ The key management system, as mentioned in Part I of this deliverable, is used as the main access control system for Alex, falls under centralised identity management.

On the other end, distributed systems are increasingly being preferred in access control. **Blockchain** is gaining leverage in access control to create a secure platform to verify credentials and attributes of employees. For instance, IBM, a global technology company, has created a tamper-proof record of employee certifications to mitigate the risk of identity fraud.[75] The immutability and transparency of blockchain make it an efficient tool for ensuring the integrity and authenticity of employee data, reducing the risk of data breaches and unauthorized access.

Blockchain technology offers promising solutions to address the security vulnerabilities of traditional Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) systems. By decentralizing certificate authorities and leveraging blockchain's immutable ledger, researchers have proposed frameworks that enhance PKI security and reliability.[76] These blockchain-based PKI systems eliminate single points of failure, provide certificate transparency, and enable rapid response to compromised certificate authorities.[77] Implementations using platforms like Geth and smart contracts demonstrate the feasibility of such systems.[76] Moreover, blockchain-based PKIs can be designed to protect user privacy by avoiding direct links between identities and public keys.[78]

Blockchain technology, by decentralising the key management offers a promising avenue for enhancing security of PKI systems. However, personal data processing via blockchains poses risks

⁵⁹ Kashmir Hill, "The Secretive Company That Might End Privacy as We Know It." The New York Times, 18 Jan. 2020, www.nytimes.com/2020/01/18/technology/clearview-privacy-facial-recognition.html. "Hyderabad: Gang Clones Fingerprints to Hack Accounts through Aadhaar-Based Pay." The Times of India, 17 June 2022, timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/hyderabad/gang-clones-fingerprints-to-hack-a/cs-through-aadhaar-based-pay/articleshow/92269356.cms. Accessed 3 Apr. 2025.

to data subject rights, as explained in Part I. In the context of access control systems, the processing would encounter the same challenges as using blockchain as a digital identity repository typically means processing many categories of personal data. However, blockchain can still be used to ensure the principle of data minimisation by storing only the hash pointers to the content data, rather than storing the raw data itself. While hashed data remains pseudonymous under the GDPR, it can be justified as a method to enhance the security, transparency, and integrity of the sensitive data in question. In other words, on-chain pseudonymised data can be seen as complementary to the off-chain data processing. This option has not only been discussed in the literature, but several institutions have suggested such solutions.[27]

For the use case at hand, each transaction on blockchain can be automatically linked via smart contracts to access certain data content on-chain. Any modification made in the on-chain data can also be logged in the blockchain layer. To put simply, while the initially processed content data is stored off-chain, any other process, including access to such data creates a new transaction, timestamp and other necessary metadata on the blockchain layer.

However, this solution might not be reliable in terms of integrity of the off-chain data. As the on-chain data will be metadata, such as the hash value linked to the off-chain data, this system would not be sufficient to prove the originality of the on-chain data. Another challenge is rooted in the difference between event chains and content blocks, where blockchain does not reflect the truth about the events. In other words, what happens in the real world or off-chain events will likely differ from what happens in the virtual world. This might cause challenges with regard to the accuracy of the broadcast data on the ledgers.[79]

4.2. THE RIGHT TO ERASURE

As outlined in Part I, certain conditions must be met to invoke the right to erasure. These conditions include situations where the data is no longer necessary, consent has been withdrawn, processing is unlawful, or legal obligations require compliance. We will not discuss consent for employee data (access control data) as explained above.

In general, it must be assessed whether data subjects can request from data controllers the complete deletion of their personal data that has been disclosed to third parties or made public by the controller. The EDPB provides several key recommendations and considerations regarding the right to erasure in the context of blockchain technology.[27]

First, the rights to erasure and objection must be built into the design. Controllers should consider this requirement in the early design phase and must continue throughout the processing lifecycle. Second, if personal data is stored on-chain, controllers must ensure it can be effectively rendered anonymous if an erasure request or objection is received. This requires that the relevant transaction data stored on-chain does not allow direct identification of the data subject, and any off-chain data that could enable indirect identification is erased.[27] Third, if consent is the legal basis for processing, the personal data must be deleted or rendered anonymous if that consent is withdrawn.[27]

5. MEASURES TO ADDRESS THE RISKS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

For blockchains, a commonly recommended approach is to off-chain process personal data. This involves storing sensitive personal information off-chain while retaining hashes or pointers to that data on-chain, thereby mitigating risks of non-compliance with the UK GDPR. Such a design aims to strike a balance between the advantages of blockchain technology and established data protection principles. Metadata, when pseudonymised, may still be stored on the blockchain to preserve

functionality while reducing identifiability. It is also essential to ensure that private keys are stored securely, as they are critical for maintaining data integrity and access control within the system.[27]

In general, when designing blockchain systems that involve the processing of personal data, it is essential to adopt a cautious and structured approach. Processing personal data using blockchains can endanger the rights of data subjects. The EDBP's recent guidelines on blockchains address some of the issues, such as data stored within a *blockchain*. The guidelines, referring to the technical and organisational measures in Article 25(2), advocate that public blockchains should only be used if necessary for at least one of the processing purposes.[27]

Regulators need to develop specific guidelines that address the unique challenges of blockchain technology. Collaborative efforts between regulatory bodies, blockchain experts, and companies can lead to practical frameworks for compliance. This includes implementing sandboxing strategies to test and evaluate the impact of design choices in a controlled environment. Additionally, a process of continuous data protection assessment should be embedded throughout the system's lifecycle, ensuring that evolving risks are identified and addressed proactively. Engaging relevant stakeholders in this process—such as data protection officers, legal experts, and end-users—helps ensure that compliance with data protection obligations is maintained while supporting innovation. While the EDBP guidelines (2025) clarify some ambiguities, they still lack specifics on how existing case law relates to blockchains. The EDBP has failed to conduct a detailed examination of roles and responsibilities. This contribution aims to address that gap, although a more comprehensive and updated analysis, considering future case law, might be needed. [27]

An alternative approach involves developing legal frameworks tailored specifically for distributed systems, which differ greatly from traditional centralised models of personal data management. Implementing sector-specific or context-aware legislation can offer more effective and nuanced governance. It would also be helpful to clarify how risks are distributed among network participants and to specify which regulations, aside from GDPR, are applicable.

Creating a cloud platform that many stakeholders can access requires adhering to specific data protection requirements in the EU. The GDPR imposes strict obligations for processing personal data, including ensuring data security and mitigating risks. On the other hand, a cursory examination of the data protection literature demonstrates a plethora of data protection issues related to multi-tenant cloud computing (MTC). MTC platforms host multiple users with access to the same infrastructure, which raises concerns regarding data security, access controls and the lawful processing of personal data, among others.[52]

The unlawful use of personal data has been a primary concern regarding MTC.[80] What follows is the risk of surveillance and function creep, where personal data is accumulated in massive storage, often creating large datasets.[81], [82] However, data security issues rank number one among the current issues.[83] In general, when tenants have access to the same platform, any coding mistake can cause significant issues in system management.[80] Accordingly, another problematic issue can be identified as the accountability debate under the GDPR. As with many multi-stakeholder technologies, the GDPR's prescription of accountability allocation, i.e., who will be responsible as the data controller in MTC platforms, is not straightforward.

In line with Article 35(9) of the GDPR, where appropriate, the data controller should seek the views of data subjects or their representatives regarding the intended processing activities, provided this does not compromise commercial interests, public interests, or the security of the processing operations. This engagement is critical in high-risk processing scenarios, as it ensures that data subjects are informed of the potential risks and that appropriate safeguards are implemented. Moreover, awareness-raising and training initiatives should be directed at data subjects to reinforce their understanding of the processing and their rights. Integrating transparency measures into the risk assessment process is crucial, as high-risk systems can easily fail without sufficient oversight and communication. If, despite the implemented safeguards, a high risk to the rights and freedoms

of individuals remains, the controller is obliged to consult the relevant data protection authority before proceeding with the processing.⁶⁰

6. CONCLUSION

This deliverable discussed the legal issues related to blockchain technologies in the context of cloud platforms. The first part focused on the legal frameworks and challenges applicable to blockchain technologies and cloud platforms in isolation. A technical overview of blockchain, typology and governance models has been explained. Following this, an overview of the regulatory framework has been provided. The focus of this section was primarily on the EU data protection framework, specifically the GDPR and the associated legal issues. It is established that, among other things, the most pressing issues in the context of blockchain are the allocation of responsibilities, i.e., who is the data controller or processor, and the implementation of the right to erasure.

Additionally, the application of evolving EU data laws that may be relevant has been briefly explained. Within this framework, relevant legal ambiguities regarding, e.g. smart contracts have been mentioned.

The second section of the first part provided an overview of cloud platforms, followed by an examination of the applicable legal framework and related issues. It is recognised that data protection accountability, including the allocation of controllership, cybersecurity, and intellectual property rights, is problematic in the context of cloud platforms.

Part II discussed more specific risks to fundamental rights and freedoms based on the provisions of the GDPR. As the NOUS use case 3 pertains to crisis management, we employed a hypothetical scenario in which blockchain and cloud solutions are deployed for crisis management purposes. This section can be seen as a preliminary data protection impact assessment for the use case.

Part II evaluates the findings and recommends strategies for both stakeholders and policymakers. Among other things, it is recommended that public blockchains should not be used to process personal data unless it is strictly necessary for the legitimate purposes of the processing. If deploying blockchain is essential, off-chain storage of personal data is recommended.

⁶⁰ Article 36(2) and Recitals 90-94 of the GDPR.

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